

Table 1. Yields of HKR228 and Basmati 370 in varietal trials at Kaul and Karnal, Haryana, India.

Year	Location	Yield (t/ha)		LSD (0.05)	CV (%)
		HKR228	Basmati 370		
1985	Kaul	4.9	3.5	0.5	6.8
	Karnal	4.7	2.9	1.2	14.8
1986	Kaul	5.2	3.0	0.3	4.0
	Karnal	5.5	4.8	0.7	6.4
1987	Kaul	6.1	4.3	0.8	6.8
1988	Kaul	4.8	3.5	0.7	8.0
1989	Kaul	5.1	3.6	0.2	2.87
	Karnal	5.5	3.4	0.4	4.02
1990	Kaul	2.8	1.1	0.1	3.20
	Karnal	4.9	2.8	0.6	7.57
Mean		4.95	3.29		

that of Basmati 370. Kernel elongation after cooking is 1.76, with 25.41% amylose content.

HKR228 is resistant to blast, stem rot, and whitebacked planthopper (Table 2).

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed

Neeraja, a high-yielding rice variety for poorly drained rainfed fields in Kerala

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In Kerala, rainfed rice is cultivated on 320,000 ha during the wet season (Apr-May to Sep-Oct). Flooding is a major problem during early crop growth.

We screened 500 entries under poorly drained conditions. After transplanting, the experimental field was flooded to 50 cm for 2 wk.

Promising cultivars were tested for yield at Pattambi and in farmers' fields.

Bangladesh line BR51315-4 was most promising, and has been released as Neeraja (Ptb 47).

Neeraja is semitall (110-120 cm), nonlodging, with 140-d duration (see table). Its grain is white and slender. Yields are 4-5 t/ha under average management (40-9-17 kg NPK/ha). Straw yields

Performance of Neeraja in station and adaptive trials.

Culture or variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./plant)	Duration (d)		Grain yield (tha)		Mean grain yield (t/ha) from adaptive trials
				Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	
Neeraja (BR51-315-4)	IR20/Pankaj	115	8	140	55	3.9	1.6	4.9
BR52-96-3	IR20/IR5	108	7	145	55	3.5	1.4	4.4
Ptb 1	Local check	137	7	140	55	1.5	—	2.7
LSD (0.05)						0.7		

Table 2. Characteristics of HKR228 and Basmati 370.

Character	HKR228	Basmati 370
Days to maturity	143	144
Plant height (cm)	116	144
Panicles (no./m ²)	251	269
Grains (no./m ²)	131	89
1 000-grain weight (g)	19.0	21.5
Brown rice (%)	77.8	73.3
Milled rice (%)	72.5	65.0
Kernel length (mm)	7.06	6.70
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.58	1.62
L/B ratio	4.47	4.13
Kernel length after cooking (mm)	12.43	13.54
Kernel elongation ratio	1.76	2.02
Alkali value	6.50	5.05
Amylose content (R)	25.41	19.84
Grain type	Long slender	Long slender
Leaf blast resistance (0-9 scale)	3.0	7.0
Stem rot resistance (0-5 scale)	2.25	2.25
Bacterial leaf blight resistance (0-9 scale)	8.0	9.0
Whitebacked planthopper resistance (0-9 scale)	1.0	0.0

are 8-10 t/ha. Ratoon yields average 1.5 t/ha within 50-55 d. It is moderately resistant to blast and sheath blight.

Neeraja is recommended for poorly drained fields and double-cropped wetlands. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Response of blue-green algae (BGA) in wetland rice culture in Himachal Pradesh, India

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We studied during wet season 1990 the effect on rice of BGA inoculation with different levels of applied N. Experimental soil was sandy loam, with pH 7.2, medium organic C (0.60%) and available N (110 kg/ha), and low available P (3.5 kg/ha).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications; plot size was 5 × 4.75 m.

Thirty-day-old seedlings of IR579 were transplanted 7 Jul 1990. Dry soil-based BGA inoculum was broadcast 10 d after transplanting. The crop was harvested 10 Oct.

A mother culture of BGA procured from the National Facility for Blue-Green Algae Collections, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, at New Delhi was multiplied in the field during June. Ten